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REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT POLICY FORMULATION THROUGH THE LENS OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPROVEMENT THROUGH WASTE MANAGEMENT AND REMEDATION

ABSTRACT

This article presents the possibilities of forming regional development policy through the prism of environmental improvement through waste management and remediation. The focus of the study is the ever-increasing amount of waste generated by people's living activities, production and trade, necessitates taking measures to reduce their total amount, reuse them and increase their recycling and recovery. At the same time, the article analyses the possibilities for the development of waste treatment technologies, the increasing possibilities for the use of waste as an alternative raw material and energy source and the reduction of the amount destined for landfill. As a consequence of these trends, interstate cooperation to solve waste management problems is increasingly intensifying and this is the focus of this paper.

KEY WORDS

development, waste, correlation, models, policy, ecology

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A22, C51, E61, H77

INTRODUCTION

The socio-economic policy implemented in Bulgaria is aimed at developing an efficient and competitive economy and full integration into European structures. Part of it is the regional development policy, as well as the effective environmental management. In 1991-1992, an extensive study on the Environmental Strategy was carried out at government level, with the assistance of the World Bank and the US Government, through the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the United States Agency for International Development (USAID). The study provided a comprehensive overview of the country's major environmental problems, the causes that led to these problems, and identified development priorities. This outlines the horizon of the need for a focused regional policy that rests on integrated environmental policies. This vision is also reflected in the newly developed specialised legislation on regional development and regional policy in the country. In practice, environmental protection is linked to the principles of sustainability - this means that economic development should not lead to irreparable damage to nature, on the one hand, and on the other hand, it is necessary to ensure that future generations are able to benefit from natural resources. Sustainable development is a realised necessity and is about integrating environmental, economic and social objectives. However, this integration is not always easy to achieve (Akimova, 2007). The emergence of sustainable development as a dominant paradigm in the late 1980s and early 1990s is a consequence of new political trends in which environmental issues in particular are coming to the fore. The Basel Convention on the Control of Transboundary Movements of Hazardous Wastes and their Disposal was adopted worldwide. Along with the provisions for the control of transboundary shipments of waste, the Convention also introduces the basic principles of waste management[2].

Implementation of an institutional waste management policy

At the European level, the main guidelines of waste management policy are outlined in the European Community Waste Management Strategy adopted in 1989, where the following principles of a "waste management hierarchy" are formulated[3]. It identified waste prevention as the first priority, followed by waste recovery through recycling and incineration with energy recovery, and finally environmentally sound disposal through incineration without energy recovery and landfilling. The second principle is 'polluter pays' and 'producer responsibility' - waste generators or producers of products that generate waste after use must bear the full cost of waste treatment. The third principle is 'best available techniques without excessive costs' (BATNEEC) - emissions from installations into the environment should be reduced as far as possible and in the most cost-effective way. The next principle is 'self-sufficiency' - each country must build a network of facilities and installations with sufficient capacity to dispose of all the waste generated on its territory. The next level is 'proximity' - waste should be disposed of as close as possible to where it is generated. To ensure waste prevention, a number of instruments are being applied, such as promoting the introduction of technologies that generate less and less hazardous waste; adopting technical standards to limit the presence of certain hazardous substances in products that generate waste; and promoting reuse systems. Environmental protection activities, and waste management in particular, must be carried out without disrupting the functions of In this respect, the principle of 'self-sufficiency' applies only to waste destined for disposal, without prohibiting the shipment of waste for recovery to another EU Member State.

In practice, the first attempts at a more targeted policy took place in the period 1992-2000, when actions related to the formation of the institutional framework, the laws and standards, the possibilities for monitoring and information provision, the policies related to restructuring, the economic and administrative instruments for implementing environmental policy were undertaken. Some specific measures have been identified to address critical environmental problems in specific areas of the country. The objectives formulated are along two main lines, firstly, to introduce new approaches and create a sound environmental management system, and secondly, to improve environmental conditions in the country's hotspots. In this direction, waste management may also prove to be an important point in the direction of improving our surroundings. It can be assumed that in the period up to 1999, national, municipal and company waste management programmes were

under way. The foundations of the legal regulation of waste management, in accordance with the requirements of European legislation, were laid with the adoption of the Act on the Limitation of the Harmful Effects of Waste on the Environment (LELWEA) in 1997, and most of its provisions are also enshrined in the current Waste Management Act (WMA) (SG No. 86 of 2003). The WEEE Act established the legal framework for waste management in the country - the types of waste to which waste management legislation applies were regulated. The definition of waste was introduced, on the basis of which the substances to be considered as waste are defined, as well as the definitions of waste producer and waste holder, which define the persons responsible for waste management. A permit regime was established for all activities related to waste management and the competent authorities - the Ministry of the Environment and Water (MoEW) and its territorial authorities the Regional Inspectorates for Environment and Water (RIEW) - were designated to issue permits and monitor their implementation. In order to collect information on waste necessary for management decision-making and effective control, a procedure for recording and reporting the quantities of waste generated and treated (municipal, construction, industrial and hazardous) was introduced and the Waste Management Information System was set up. In practice, during this period, attempts to build or are in an advanced stage of preparation for the construction of basic infrastructure facilities as part of the system for integrated waste management in the country. Organized household waste collection covers about 77% of the country's population. It is noted that there is a good basis and potential in the country regarding the development of the necessary statistical system for waste, in this direction and registers of landfills and old pollution with waste [5].

One of the most serious problems in and around settlements in the country, both from an aesthetic and a hygienic point of view, is waste. The large and indiscriminate littering cannot be covered by the existing information system, but this is hardly necessary. Averaged over the period 1991-2001, information on total municipal waste shows approximately 3.2 million tons of waste per year or about 390 kg per capita [6]. The latter, compared with the figures for Greece (310), Portugal (330), Hungary (387) and Poland (338), shows first of all that a systematic waste management policy needs to be enforced in the country [7].

On waste management issues, a series of problems related to pollution in and around waste settlements is one of the most serious aesthetic and hygiene problems of the country. As of 1999, the number of villages covered by the organized garbage collection system was still small. Separate collection and treatment of hazardous waste from households, and in many cases from hospitals, is not universally carried out. There is no system and installations for the treatment of old vehicles. There is no separate collection and recycling of packaging waste and other household waste. There is a lack of a national policy, installations and an established system for the treatment of biodegradable waste. There is no national and local policy on household agricultural waste. The administrative capacity of control structures, information collection and planning possibilities are insufficient in relation to the requirements of the adopted and pending legislation. The municipal waste fees collected do not cover all the costs of collection and disposal according to the legal requirements. The issue of sewage sludge remains open. All these emerging challenges for waste management, as well as Bulgaria's invitation to become a member of the European Union, make it necessary to improve waste management policies [8].

In the period 1999-2008, three laws related to the development of regions in Bulgaria were successively adopted. This helps to clearly delineate the functions and responsibilities of the central institutions with regard to the management of environmental components. However, insufficient administrative capacity of the central authorities for the preparation and implementation of regulatory documents was identified during the period. This is related to insufficient coordination between the different institutions concerned with environmental protection in the implementation of joint policies and in the establishment of programmes and regulatory documents affecting different areas of public life [9].

The reasons for the increasing attention of international organisations, institutes, political and scientific circles, companies and citizens in the field of waste economics are rooted in the processes

taking place worldwide, in the development of the issue itself over time and in its importance. In the last few decades, waste management has evolved from an industry primarily concerned with the processing of waste and its final disposal to one that contributes significantly to energy saving and material recovery. On these issues, from a regional development point of view, there is a decentralisation of competences without reciprocal provision of financial instruments to realise responsibilities. This leads to insufficient capacity in municipal administrations to deal with the challenges facing them - lack of ecologists in many municipal administrations, lack of control bodies, although they have control functions, there remain uncovered areas, lack of competence to develop tender documents and concessions. New problems are highlighted such as the need to build an integrated system of waste treatment facilities. Establishing mechanisms for the functioning of the separate collection, recycling and reuse system. Significantly improving the cleanliness of Bulgaria's settlements. This requires a closer link between environmental waste and regional development and effective territorial management[10].

Regional development and environmental protection

In the context of the new legislation on regional development, strategic guidelines have been proposed to improve the activities, of regional and district councils, as bodies for the implementation of state policy for regional development, in level 2 regions and districts through decentralisation and subsidiarity. Strengthening the powers of regional and district councils to improve capacity, through strategic planning, improving regional coordination between different sectoral development policies, programmes and projects, improving the system for monitoring and implementing documents and assessing the impact on the development of the regions. Allocating resources to regional and district development councils to develop their functionality and effectiveness, and to support the activity of carrying out specialised studies of areas with geographical handicaps. This includes the improved environmental situation. The aim of developing an environmentally friendly, competitive, green economy as a contribution to sustainable development and resource efficiency is part of the EU measures to achieve the objectives of the strategy. The European Union seeks to integrate the objectives of the Sustainable Development Strategy into all its policies. The term 'green economy' was first coined by D. The concept of a green economy was first introduced by Dr. Pearce in 1989 in his book 'A Blueprint for a Green Economy', which set out the characteristics and principles of the concept of sustainable development[11]. The green economy has been proposed as a policy approach to help address the problems of slowing economic growth and job loss, as well as the continuing degradation of environmental quality and ecosystem degradation. However, this can only happen in a context of stable and effective regional policy. In these conditions, it is important for the spatial development of the national territory to achieve the necessary meso-level capacity. In practice, this means empowering the regional development management authorities in Level 2 regions and districts. At these levels, development policies and the implementation of modern strategies should be able to be implemented, designed to highlight the leading role of regional and district councils in the implementation of development strategies in line with international standards and best practices for sustainable integrated regional development. In this direction, we can adopt the following working title for regional policy: 'policy pursued at regional level by the state. It establishes sustainable integrated development of regions and municipalities through a system of regulatory documents, resources and actions aimed at reducing inter-regional and intra-regional disparities"[12]. Regional policy is implemented by executive authorities at national and regional level. The regulation of the municipality as an administrative-territorial unit in which local self-government is carried out, guaranteeing the right to property, an independent budget and association of municipalities, as well as the definition of the bodies for their management is also essential for the formation of regional policy [13]. Thus, at the level of regional development, it is necessary to move towards the implementation of a regional policy defined as "Sustainable Integrated Regional and Local Development". This requires a definition of this concept. In our case, Sustainable Integrated Regional and Local Development will be understood as the implementation of a policy that aims to: bring about targeted changes in living and working conditions in areas through social and economic action

in line with environmental protection and protection against discrimination. This is necessitated by the need to establish clearer rules and procedures for the development, adoption, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of strategic planning documents for regional and local development is simplified hierarchical relationship and coherence between the documents in order to improve coordination between the bodies that develop and adopt them. In order to implement the State policy on environmental protection and to integrate it successfully into sectoral policies and regional development management, the necessary regulatory and institutional environment has been formally established. According to the author's opinion, the term "environmental assessment" does not sufficiently reflect the essence of the concept of "strategic environmental assessment"[14], which is the source of a series of objective difficulties in the implementation of the legislation on environmental assessments of strategic documents in Bulgaria. For our study we assume that Ecology is a scientific discipline explaining the interrelations between living organisms and the environment. Today it is seen as a social science, dealing with the relationship between societal development and the problems it causes in the environment. Provided that we consider ecology within the framework of the national space, it is necessary to derive the concept of state policy. State policy is thus understood as the imposition of purposeful actions by state bodies in a set of ideas, principles and concrete actions to achieve certain goals. Policy is determined by objective and subjective factors. State environmental policy is a purposeful activity of state bodies to protect the environment. It is characterized by -always and determined by law and at the same time law is the most important instrument for the implementation of state policy.

Having defined the concept of environmental policy and defined its focus on regional development, it is necessary to define the changes occurring in regional development through environmental change. This also means to bring out the concept of environmental change. Thus, for the present study, we can assume that environmental change is a spatial change that leads to a modification of the quality of life of people related to biodiversity, as well as the imposition of policy to restore natural ecosystems or their optimal maintenance. In alteration, the negative effects are permanent, one or more components are damaged and the quality of life is impaired. Alteration occurs through the accumulation of pollutants. Thus, we can derive an eightfold working definition related to an emission standard. By an emission limit value, we will mean various values for the mass of pollutants and other negative factors that should not be exceeded for one or more specified periods of time.

Thus, in the spatial modelling of the nature of human development, the nature of the contradictions in the system "society-environment-regional development" comes to the fore. It is focused by the need to function an effective regional policy that can solve local and global environmental problems by reflecting on their sustainability in the state of contemporary societal development. In this direction, the management of optads, which is part of the structure of environmental policy, is embedded as an essential frequency of the local public works policy related to the solution of regional development problems. Viewed from another aspect, regional development can be defined as "a conscious activity of society aimed at coordinating and regulating the processes taking place in a given territory in order to harmonise them and create optimum conditions for the work, living and recreation of the population, and the development of the well-being of workers on the basis of increasing the efficiency of social production"[15].

In this direction, it is necessary to derive a working concept of regional development policy. The policy of regional development is based on the implementation of targeted activities and measures impacting socially, economically and infrastructurally in the territorial socio-economic system taking into account the regulatory relations in the national space. In practice, this shows the integrated nature of regional development, which defines the scope of processes such as regional planning, forecasting and programming, as well as structuring the system of regional relations. In this direction, it is necessary to consider the functional characteristics of the development of territorial communities within the national space. In the context, of the scientific research, their distinctive characteristics and properties are summarized. This predetermines the necessity, in order to effectively and efficiently manage regional development, to create mechanisms for ensuring publicity and

transparency at all levels, which requires the operation of a unified information system for the management of regional development, which should also include waste management [16].

The unified information system for regional development management includes an integrated information system for strategic planning of regional and local development and an information system for monitoring the implementation of strategic planning documents for regional development. Well-being, with less use of resources, and generation of less waste, is not only possible, but mandatory. A steadily growing world population is increasingly exploiting limited natural resources, which limits development opportunities. Waste, on the one hand, is generated by the use of resources or products and, on the other hand, it has negative effects on the environment as a result of its processing or disposal. Thus, all the strategic and planning documents for regional development include measures and activities that not only take into account the existing protected areas of the adjacent territory, but also offer opportunities for their better management and conservation of natural ecosystems with a great diversity of plant and animal species and habitats, with characteristic and remarkable landscapes, and sites of inanimate nature[17].

Regional development management and waste issues

In the management of regional development in terms of waste problems, the link can be broken between economic growth and the increasing use of resources, with negative impacts on people and nature. This brings with it the demand for the utility of environmental policy. This implies that for the regional development system to function successfully, it is also necessary to implement a waste prevention policy. This policy should lead to the prevention of the negative impact of waste on regional development. It is particularly important to emphasise that the prevention of the negative impact of waste in the regional development system must have a high priority. The greatest environmental pressures arise in the production of a product and it is for this reason that these pressures are reduced by waste prevention measures. In addition, the harmful effects of incineration, transport and storage are also reduced in this way. Ultimately, waste prevention means not generating waste, not producing products that then have to be recycled or disposed of. Different options for waste treatment are always associated with difficulties and environmental burdens. Waste does not simply disappear, but through landfilling and incineration, only changes as a substance. Incineration, for example, even with the most modern technologies, produces emissions and/or residues that must be stored. All landfilling is an interference with nature, and harmful effects on the environment cannot be ruled out. In the best case, the waste is recovered, but even in this case there are pressures due to the use of energy and water. Therefore, the only adequate countermeasure to the waste problem is the action taken to prevent the generation of waste, which is part of the necessary transition to sustainable use of existing resources. It must be implemented in a way that does not negatively affect the economic situation. Thus, for the effective management of regional development, environmental policies need to combine spatial and economic approaches in order to achieve the environmental requirements for the functioning of regional systems.

In this direction, the following should be emphasized in relation to regional development and regional policy:

First of all, the object of study in regional development from an economic hunger point of view is positioned within the scope and content of the regional economy and the governance of territorial communities. Regional development is seen as, a system formed by the socio-economic and natural elements within a given territory, on the one hand, and on the other hand with the intentions and desires of society, formulated in a normative framework and expressed through regional planning and targeted actions by the state towards its regions .

Secondly, the available, complex nature of regional development implies linking the analysis of categories and concepts that set the methodological framework for the implementation of territorial policies, such as forecasting, planning, programming, as well as clarifying the territorial characteristics where there is an interaction of natural, social and economic factors .

Thirdly, the focus of regional policy has different levels, making it necessary to approach individual policies with specific tools. In this direction, waste management also has its focus on the implementation of European Union (EU), national and regional policies in order to achieve effective integrated territorial management[18]. Fourthly, the institutional environment developed has a direct impact on public policies for regional development in political, technological, economic, social, cultural and environmental aspects. At the same time, the purpose of state policy for regional development is to anticipate local development policies in the territory by adapting the relevant institutional environment. In the direction of the "regional development-environment-human resources" nexus, the role of the human factor is often underestimated, especially in terms of strategic planning and management of regional development.

CONCLUSION

Fairness is paramount to achieving this. To a large extent, we can assume that by creating partnerships in the use of EU funds, environmental improvement will be a legitimate outcome. In this area are also the directions for future research on the subject area of the thesis, concerning the study of possible mechanisms for the creation of effective, meaningful and sustainable partnership and teamwork of actors in the implementation of regional development policy. Its successful implementation is an objective need because the results are visible and significant for people, for what their standard of living is and could be if they as citizens, members of NGOs, associations or professionals and administrators express their active position by participating in the elaboration, discussion, adoption and implementation of regional and local development strategies and plans. In this way, all regions will be able to develop their potential for economic and social development and all citizens will feel the beneficial effects of regional policy, regardless of where they live. Nature is our life-support system, so we must look after it. We share resources such as water, air, natural habitats and the species that live in them, as well as environmental standards for their protection. In this direction, environmental policy and waste management, respectively, are part of regional development management and need to be further studied and made an essential priority of territorial development. Solving a series of severe environmental problems that are not only global but also regional in nature. The issues related to environmental protection and the tendency towards the further consolidation and implementation of the concept of sustainable development is the main factor that also determines the place of waste management in the field of regional development and requires a new strategic approach to the enforcement of integrated management.

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